

THE ROLE OF PARENTAL ENGAGEMENT IN REFLECTION JOURNALING AND ITS INFLUENCE ON THE ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF GRADE 11 STUDENTS IN GENERAL MATHEMATICS: A CASE STUDY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18287488>

ABSTRACT

This study explored the impact of parents' engagement in reflective journaling on the academic performance of Grade 11 students in General Mathematics at Marikit High School, highlighting the role of parental involvement as a potential factor in enhancing student achievement. This study employed qualitative research design, utilizing a survey questionnaire with an open-ended item to collect data from participants. The instrument was subjected to a validation process in which experts' feedback was incorporated. A purposive sampling technique was applied to select Grade 11 students enrolled in General Mathematics across different academic strands at Marikit High School. Thematic analysis was then used to interpret and analyze the data gathered from the participants. The findings of the study highlight parental involvement as a critical factor in the academic achievement and learning processes of students, particularly in General Mathematics. Results further reveal that Reflective Journaling (RJ) functions as a valuable pedagogical tool, enhancing student learning while providing parents with a structured means to monitor academic progress and developmental milestones. By reinforcing home-school collaboration, RJ—combined with parental engagement—emerges as a significant contributor to student achievement. Moreover, RJ offers parents an effective avenue to guide and support their children's academic growth, even in situations where they are not physically present in school. Based on the findings, the study recommends strengthening parental engagement programs, institutionalizing Reflective Journaling (RJ) as a pedagogical tool, and promoting sustained home-school collaboration. It further suggests providing training for teachers on RJ implementation, encouraging policy support for

parental involvement, and pursuing future research to expand and deepen the understanding of RJ's role in student achievement.

Keywords: *Parental engagement, Reflection journaling, and Academic achievement*

INTRODUCTION

Parents' involvement through reflective journaling is necessary for the progress of the child in their life especially in their studies. This is very useful for the child that needs attention in their studies or with educational need. Such actions of parents would be helpful for them in identifying the needs of their child in school. This would help the parents be informed regarding the performance of their children in school. For children, reflective journaling can help the student's performance in school, and it also helps strengthen the relationship between parents and students. The family involvement in students' schooling is a positive and important factor that contributes to academic achievements (Martinez, 2015).

Parental involvement in school activities is necessary for the development of the students in terms of academic. They can also help the students do their homework and they can be able to identify the needs of their children in their studies. They can also determine the performance of their children in school. Parental support is really necessary towards the child because through their support the learners will be motivated and encouraged to do good in their studies. Children will feel that they are loved and accepted. The confidence of the learners will be boosted if parents have constant physical affection for their children.

The parents' involvement in school activities would be beneficial to the learners and the teacher as well in school activities. Collaboration between parents and teachers is really needed for the development of the learners, especially in their studies. Through this study the learner will be improved and the problem in their academics or studies will be addressed somehow because there will be involvement of parents. Teachers would not be more worried about the follow up of the learning of the learners because parents will take that part.

Parent involvement in school has been demonstrated as key factor for children's academic outcomes. They have also mentioned that parental involvement in school has long been heralded as an important and positive variable on children's academic and socioemotional development (Lara and Saracosti, 2019).

One of the major challenges identified by researchers in relation to students' unsatisfactory academic performance, particularly in mathematics, is their poor learning and retention, which often stems from insufficient motivation and encouragement provided by parents. Studies have consistently shown that parental involvement and support play a critical role in fostering students' persistence, confidence, and achievement

in mathematics. Conversely, the absence of parental encouragement has been linked to diminished motivation, weaker retention of mathematical concepts, and lower academic outcomes (Hernández-Padilla et al, 2023; Rulida et al., 2024; Mondigo & Uchang, 2025).

Although several strategies have been introduced to address the persistent issue of unsatisfactory academic performance, the problem remains unresolved, suggesting that critical actions for a realistic and sustainable solution are still lacking. In the Philippines, major initiatives such as *Drop Everything and Read (DEAR) Day*, *Catch-Up Friday*, the *Academic Recovery and Accessible Learning (ARAL) Program*, and *Isang Kaibigan Book* have been implemented to enhance learners' academic outcomes. Despite these efforts, challenges in the quality of education continue to persist, particularly in core subjects such as mathematics and reading comprehension (Department of Education [DepEd], 2022; Mateo, 2023; World Bank, 2021).

The inconsistency of parental support and involvement in students' academic activities has been shown to negatively affect their academic performance, particularly in General Mathematics. Consistent parental engagement is essential in fostering motivation, reinforcing learning, and improving retention of mathematical concepts. When such involvement is lacking, students often experience reduced confidence, weaker study habits, and lower achievement outcomes. Prior studies affirm that parental participation plays a critical role in enhancing mathematics performance and overall academic success, while its absence contributes to unsatisfactory learning results (Hernández-Padilla et al, 2023; Rulida et al, 2024; Mondigo & Uchang, 2025).

The researchers have thought of the solution to the problem of the learners in their academic, especially in General Mathematics subject. The researcher had thought of hands-on participation of parents or guardians in the process of learning students most especially at this situation of the new normal. The solution that the researcher had thought somehow could help address this problem is the REFLECTION JOURNAL with the involvement of parents and guardians. In this study, the learner will write everything that he/she would have learned in daily lessons. The daily activity of the learner will be monitored by the parent and guardian, and it will be signed by them. All activities will be compiled and submitted at the end of the semester. This study was conducted at Marikit High School, and the participants were the students that are currently enrolled in the present school year, S.Y. 2025-2026. The researchers had thought of this study to ensure the participation of parents in the studies of students. The study has a lot of social benefits for both parents and students. They could have strong bonding within the family and the parent, or the guardian of the student can guide them which is the most important participation of parents-to help and guide their child or children. The parents and the guardian will be updated on the daily activities of the learners. Through reflective journaling parents and guardians will know if their child is actively participating in the discussion of daily lessons. The study will not just help students improve their performance in General Mathematics but also in other subjects especially English and Filipino that require to improve their skills in writing. The benefits of keeping reflective journal writing are on improving English writing skills, increasing motivation, enhancing creativity, and critical thinking among university students (Farrah, 2012). The importance of reflective journals in the literature promotes student's learning, developing writing skills,

assessing students' reflection level (Ahmed, 2019). Definitely in this study, the writing skills of students will somehow be enhanced. The possible result of this study could be used in some action planning especially to address problems like poor academic performance of students that lead to some serious problems-rate of dropouts. If the result could help improve the academic performance of students, then it can be used to planning on how to improve the national achievement test performance of students. The researchers had chosen this study that may help students improve their academic performance in General Mathematics subject.

Research Questions

1. What part do parents play in Reflective Journaling (RJ) for General Mathematics?
2. In what ways can Reflective Journaling (RJ) help learners learn in General Mathematics?
3. How does reflective journaling, with parental involvement, contribute to a student's academic performance in General Mathematics?

METHODOLOGY

This outlines the research methodology, including the instruments utilized, procedures for their validation and administration, and the approach employed for thematic data analysis.

Research Design

This study employed a qualitative case study design to investigate the influence of parental engagement in students' reflection journaling on the academic performance of Grade 11 learners in General Mathematics. The case study approach was chosen to gain a deep and contextualized understanding of the phenomenon within its natural educational setting, allowing for rich insights into the dynamics between students, their parents, and reflective learning practices.

Participants were selected through purposive sampling and included Grade 11 students enrolled in General Mathematics, their respective parents or guardians, and two subject teachers. The research was conducted in Marikit High School, a senior high school located in Marikina City, where reflection journaling is embedded in mathematics-related activities.

Data collection involved two primary methods: a student survey and document analysis of reflection journals that had been signed or annotated by parents. The survey instrument was designed to examine key themes such as parental involvement, feedback mechanisms, emotional support, and perceived effects on student learning. Meanwhile, the reflection journals were reviewed to identify indicators of parental input, levels of student self-awareness, and evidence of conceptual development in mathematics.

Thematic analysis was used to interpret the data. Responses and journal entries were coded inductively to uncover recurring patterns and emergent themes. This qualitative approach enabled the researcher to explore subtle and meaningful connections between parental engagement and student academic outcomes, offering valuable insights that may inform future teaching strategies and strengthen parent-school collaboration.

Sampling Procedure and Participants

This study employed a purposive sampling method, involving only Grade 11 students enrolled in General Mathematics from sections directly taught by the two-mathematics teacher-researchers. Participation was restricted to these specific groups under the researchers' instruction. To enhance the depth of analysis, participants were grouped according to their class sections and gender.

Table 1. Respondents of the study as to their sections and genders

Respondents	MALE		FEMALE		TOTAL	
	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
11 ANALYTICAL	1	3	1	5	2	8
11 ASPIRING	1	3	2	5	3	8
11 HARMONIOUS	2	5	3	8	5	14
11 HELPFUL	2	5	4	11	6	16
11 HOLISTIC	2	5	3	8	5	14
11 HOSPITABLE	2	5	4	11	6	16
11 TRANSCENDENTS	3	8	2	5	5	14
11 STRATEGIC	2	5	2	5	4	11
Total	15	41	22	59	37	100

Instruments

The study utilized a survey questionnaire to gather insights into the participants' perspectives on how reflective journaling influenced their academic performance in General Mathematics. The instrument was specifically developed and validated in alignment with the objectives of the research. It comprised two main sections: the first focused on the demographic profile of the respondents, consisting of five items; the second explored their views on the role of parental engagement in reflection journaling and its impact on the academic achievement of Grade 11 students in General Mathematics, featuring three open-ended questions.

Data Collection

To gather data from the participants, an open-ended survey questionnaire was utilized. Prior to its administration, the instrument underwent validation through expert consultation to ensure the relevance and clarity of its items. Once validated, the questionnaire was distributed to the selected participants. After the responses were completed and retrieved, the data were compiled and analyzed using thematic analysis. The researchers adhered to a structured timeline encompassing the proposal development, data collection, and presentation of the study's findings.

Table 2. Time frame for the collection of data and presentation of the result

ACTIVITIES	MAY -DECEMBER 2025										
	May-2025	JUNE 1-15, 2025	JUNE 16-OCTOBER 31, 2025	Nov-2025			December 2025				
Accomplishment of Research Proposal											
Validation and Revision of Research Instruments											
Writing Journal and Collection of Data											
Initial findings											
Revision of parts submitted during the proposal											
Data analysis											
Tabular presentation of the data											
Final findings, conclusions, and recommendations											
Completion of the research manuscript in an IMRAD format											
Accomplishment and Submission of the final copy of the research											

Data Analysis Framework

Given the qualitative nature of this study, the researchers adopted framework analysis as the guiding methodological approach. This analytical framework is well-suited for qualitative research, offering a structured yet flexible process for managing and interpreting complex data. Upon completion of data collection, the researchers systematically organized the raw data in preparation for thematic analysis.

Using qualitative data analysis techniques, the researchers identified and developed codes, categories, and themes that emerged from the dataset. This process involved iterative coding and categorization, followed by thematic mapping to uncover deeper patterns and meanings. The results were then refined and interpreted through thematic analysis to generate meaningful insights aligned with the study's objectives.

Qualitative data analysis refers to the systematic process of collecting, organizing, and interpreting non-numerical data to reveal underlying patterns, themes, and insights. It enables researchers to make sense of open-ended responses, interviews, and other forms of unstructured data (Dye, 2025).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 3. Summary of Themes

CODES	CATEGORIES	THEMES	DESCRIPTION OF THEMES
Supportive Role	Supportive Role	Parental Involvement in Learning General Mathematics	Parental engagement in reflective journaling refers to the active involvement of parents in guiding and supporting their child's self-assessment and learning reflections. This collaborative practice enhances the student's understanding of mathematical concepts, fosters confidence, and contributes positively to their academic achievement in General Mathematics, particularly among Grade 11 students.
Learning Support			
Foundational Guidance			
Support and Motivation			
Crucial Support Role			
Supportive Guidance			
Emotional Support and Encouragement			
Guidance and Support	Foundational Guidance		
Trusted Guidance			
Guidance and Assistance			
Guidance and Assistance			
Trusted Guidance			
Guidance and Encouragement			
Guidance Through Challenges	Performance Consultation		
Personal Guidance			
Recognition of Achievement			
Performance Consultation			
Review and Approval			
Monitoring Progress			
Supervision			

Reflective Practice			
Progress Monitoring			
Active Involvement	Active Involvement		
Active Involvement			
Active Monitoring			
Active Participation			
Mentorship Role			
Emotional and Academic Support	Learning Support		
Encouragement to Excel			
Guidance in Learning			
Learning Reflection Support			
Encouragement and Motivation			
Supportive Learning Partner			
Encouragement in Learning			
Guidance and Encouragement			
Conceptual Understanding	Cognitive Development	Reflective Journaling (RJ) helps learning in General Mathematics	
Enhanced Recall			
Review of Strategies			
Memory Reinforcement			
Lesson Recollection			
Mastery of Concepts			
Deep Understanding			
Improved Understanding			
Clearer Understanding			
Skill Strengthening			
Deeper Understanding			
Enhanced Comprehension	Emotional Engagement and Motivation		
Mastery of Topics			
Lesson Recall			
Memory Enhancement			

Deepened Understanding				
Deep Learning				
Deeper Comprehension				
Comprehensive Learning	Learning Process Structuring			
Comprehensive Learning				
Clarity Through Writing				
Deep Conceptual Thinking				
Deep Conceptual Thinking				
Deep Conceptual Thinking				
Comprehensive Understanding				
Improvement Awareness				
Experience Review		Self-Assessment and Metacognition		
Perspective Sharing				
Critical Thinking Development				
Thoughtful Learning				
Organized Thinking				
Highlighting What Helps				
Performance-enhancing	Academic Growth	The contribution of Reflective Journaling and Parental Involvement on Academic Achievement in General Mathematics		
Performance-enhancing				

Performance-enhancing			
Performance-boosting			
Improvement-driven	Academic Impact		
Improvement-focused			
Application-focused			
Improvement-driven			
Skill-building			
Success-focused			
Improvement-driven			
Success-focused			
Improvement-driven			
Achievement-oriented			
Improvement-driven			
Confidence-boosting	Confidence-building		
Confidence-boosting			
Reinforcing	Learning Impact		
Success-oriented			
Growth-oriented			
Understanding-enhancing	Learning Outcomes		
Understanding-deepening	Learning Process		
Understanding-deepening			
Improvement-driven	Skill Development		
Improvement-driven			

Conclusions

Parental Involvement in Learning General Mathematics

The findings of this study indicate that parental involvement constitutes a critical factor in the academic achievement and learning processes of students, particularly in the subject of General Mathematics. The results underscore the essential roles that parents fulfill, which include providing supportive functions, offering foundational guidance, engaging in performance consultation, demonstrating active participation, and extending consistent learning support. Such involvement not only fosters a conducive learning environment but also strengthens students' motivation, confidence, and

persistence in mastering mathematical concepts. By actively participating in their children's education, parents contribute to the development of effective study habits, reinforce classroom instruction, and encourage the pursuit of academic excellence. Consequently, the study highlights that parental engagement is indispensable in shaping students' cognitive growth and overall performance in mathematics, thereby affirming its significance as a cornerstone of educational success (Mondigo & Uchang, 2025; Hernández-Padilla et al, 2023; Rulida et al, 2024).

Reflective Journaling (RJ) helps learn in General Mathematics

Based on the responses of the participants, the findings of this study reveal that Reflective Journaling (RJ) serves as a valuable pedagogical tool in enhancing students' learning, particularly in General Mathematics. Reflective Journaling (RJ) provides a structured avenue through which parents can monitor and track the academic progress and developmental milestones of their children, thereby reinforcing home-school collaboration. Moreover, RJ contributes significantly to students' academic growth by fostering cognitive development, strengthening emotional engagement and motivation, facilitating the structuring of the learning process, and promoting self-assessment and metacognitive awareness. These outcomes are consistent with prior studies which emphasize that reflective journal writing enhances critical thinking, mathematical communication skills, and overall achievement in mathematics (Junsay, 2016). Furthermore, reflective practices in mathematics education have been shown to cultivate higher order thinking and support learners in connecting mathematical concepts to broader contexts (Aquino, 2025).

The contribution of Reflective Journaling and Parental Involvement on Academic Achievement in General Mathematics

The results of this study, as reflected in the survey responses of the participants, indicate that Reflective Journaling (RJ), combined with parental involvement, plays a significant role in the academic achievements of students, particularly in General Mathematics. RJ serves as an effective pedagogical tool that not only supports students' learning but also provides parents with a means to guide and monitor their children's academic progress, even in instances when they are not physically present in school. In this regard, RJ functions as a communication bridge between teachers and parents, ensuring that the developmental trajectory of students is consistently observed and reinforced. Furthermore, when integrated with parental engagement, RJ contributes to multiple dimensions of student learning, including academic growth, confidence-building, skill development, and the structuring of learning processes.

These findings align with prior research emphasizing the importance of reflective practices in fostering metacognitive awareness and academic performance (Junsay & Gerada, 2016), as well as studies highlighting the critical role of parental involvement in enhancing mathematics achievement and overall learning outcomes (Hernández-Padilla et al, 2023; Rulida et al., 2024)

Recommendations

1. Strengthen Parental Engagement Programs. Schools should design structured initiatives that actively involve parents in the learning process of General Mathematics. Workshops, orientation sessions, and parent-teacher conferences can emphasize the importance of consistent parental support in fostering students' motivation, confidence, and academic achievement (Mondigo & Uchang, 2025; Hernández-Padilla et al., 2023).

2. Institutionalize Reflective Journaling (RJ) as a Pedagogical Tool. Teachers are encouraged to integrate Reflective Journaling into mathematics instruction as a means of promoting metacognitive awareness, self-assessment, and critical thinking. RJ should be standardized as part of classroom practice, allowing students to reflect on their learning progress while enabling parents to monitor academic development (Junsay, 2016; Aquino, 2025).

3. Promote Home–School Collaboration through RJ. Reflective Journaling can serve as a communication bridge between teachers and parents. Schools should establish systems where journals are regularly reviewed by both educators and parents, ensuring that students' learning trajectories are consistently observed and reinforced (Rulida et al., 2024).

4. Provide Training for Teachers on RJ Implementation. Professional development programs should be offered to mathematics teachers to enhance their ability to utilize RJ effectively. Training should focus on guiding students in reflective writing, linking reflections to mathematical concepts, and using journals as formative assessment tools (Aquino, 2025).

5. Encourage Policy Support for Parental Involvement. Educational policymakers should recognize parental involvement as a cornerstone of academic success and integrate it into national education strategies. Policies should incentivize schools to adopt practices that strengthen parental participation in mathematics learning (Hernández-Padilla et al, 2023).

6. Future Research Directions. Further studies should explore the long-term impact of combining Reflective Journaling and parental involvement on mathematics achievement across different grade levels. Comparative studies between schools that implement RJ with strong parental engagement and those that do not could provide deeper insights into its effectiveness.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study was conducted in accordance with ethical research standards. Prior to data collection, formal approval was obtained from the Division Office of the Department of Education–Marikina, specifically from the Schools Division Superintendent and the Chief Education Supervisor. Informed consent was secured from all participants, with

parental signatures confirming their awareness of the study's objectives, procedures, potential risks and benefits, and their right to withdraw at any time without consequence.

To maintain confidentiality, all participant names and responses were anonymized. Additionally, to protect the identity of the participating institution, a pseudonym—Marikit High School—was used in place of the actual school's name.

Acknowledgments

The researchers extend their profound gratitude to Almighty God, whose divine guidance and provision enabled the completion of this study. Sincere appreciation is also conveyed to the leadership of the Department of Education—Marikina City, particularly Dr. Alejandro G. Ibañez, Schools Division Superintendent, and Dr. Elizalde Q. Cena, Chief Education Supervisor, for granting the necessary approval to conduct this action research within the Division of Marikina City.

The researchers are deeply thankful to Dr. Jeffrey C. Trinidad, Principal of Marikina High School, and Mr. Ferdinand S. Santos, Assistant Principal, for their unwavering support and encouragement throughout the research process. Special thanks are also extended to Ms. Marites C. Bactad, Senior High School English Teacher at Parang High School, for her valuable time and expertise in proofreading the manuscript and contributing to the refinement of this study.

REFERENCES

- Ahmed (2019). Students' Reflective Journaling: An Impactful Strategy That Informs Instructional Practices in an EFL Writing University Context in Qatar. *Reflective Practice*, 20, 483-500.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/14623943.2019.1638246>
- Aquino (2025). Reflective learning resource material in mathematics. In: M.S. Carandang (Ed.), *Teaching & Learning Beyond the Classroom* (pp. 240-258). Institute of Industry and Academic Research Incorporated.
<https://doi.org/10.53378/09.25.008>. Retrieved from https://iiari.org/online_book/.
- Department of Education (DepEd). (2022). *DepEd launches Catch-Up Fridays to improve learning outcomes*. Retrieved from <https://www.deped.gov.ph>
- Dye (2025, February 20). *Qualitative data analysis: Step-by-step guide (manual vs. automatic)*. Retrieved from <https://getthematic.com/insights/qualitative-data-analysis/>
- Farrah (2012). The Impact of Peer Feedback on Improving the Writing Skills Among Hebron University Students. *An-Najah University Journal for Research - Humanities*. 26. 179-210. 10.35552/0247-026-001-008.
- Hernández et al (2023). Parental participation and parents' support: effects on mathematics achievement, 2018 national assessment of learning, Mexico. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 14. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1154470>. Retrieved from <https://scispace.com/papers/>.

- Junsay (2016). Reflective Learning and Prospective Teachers' Conceptual Understanding, Critical Thinking, Problem Solving, and Mathematical Communication Skills. *Research in Pedagogy*, v6 n2 p43-58 2016. Retrieved from <https://eric.ed.gov/>.
- Junsay & Gerada (2016). *The effect of reflective journal writing to students' critical thinking and mathematical communication skills*. Central Philippine University. Retrieved from <https://pidswebs.pids.gov.ph>.
- Lara & Saracostti (2019). Effect of Parental Involvement on Children's Academic Achievement in Chile. *Frontiers in Psychology*. 10. 10.3389/fpsyg.2019.01464.
- Martinez (2015). *Parent involvement and its affects on student academic achievement*. California State University, Stanislaus. <https://books.google.com.ph/>
- Mateo (2023, March 3). DepEd rolls out Academic Recovery and Accessible Learning (ARAL) program. *The Philippine Star*. Retrieved from <https://www.philstar.com>
- Mondigo & Uchang (2025). PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT AND MATHEMATICS PROFICIENCY AMONG HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS. 3. 10.17613/zrmhc-y7950. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/>
- Rulida et al (2024). Parents' Involvement, Mathematical Skills, and Students' Mathematics Performance. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 27(1), 20–30. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13986128>. Retrieved from <https://zenodo.org/records/13986128>.
- World Bank. (2021). *Improving student learning outcomes in the Philippines: Analysis and recommendations*. Washington, DC: World Bank Group. Retrieved from <https://documents.worldbank.org>